

Discourse on Media Portrayal of Migration in Africa

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Abstract

This paper adopted the descriptive method to highlight certain global and local media portrayals of migration in Africa. The researcher adopted library research method. It was found that media portrayal of African migrants in South Africa as criminals and job-stealers has fueled xenophobia. Similarly, in countries like Libya and Morocco, local attitudes toward sub-Saharan migrants have worsened due to media-fueled stereotypes. More so, migrants are reduced to passive figures in the media, reinforcing the idea that they are problems to be managed rather than people with agency and goals. It was concluded that the stereotypical depictions of immigrant populations in the media represent a risk-fraught area in which prejudices may inadvertently be furthered. Amongst others, the paper recommended that the media need to avoid unfair prejudicial depictions and start presenting immigrant populations as well-rounded cultural groups, the media may be capable of providing a positive arena for diversity, cultural exchange and acculturation.

Keywords: Media, Portray, Migration And African Culture